

Unlocking Potential: Ferroptosis Inhibitors as Promising Strategies for Ischemic Stroke Therapy

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ABSTRACT

Ischemic stroke is responsible for a lot of mortality and disability and is primarily due to reduced blood flow to the brain, thus leading to oxidative stress, inflammation, and death of neuronal cells. Recent studies posit ferroptosis, which is known as an iron-dependent form of programmed cell death, as a major player in the pathophysiology of ischemic stroke. Ferroptosis occurs as a result of iron overload, excessive lipid peroxidation, and dysfunction of glutathione peroxidase 4 (GPX4), collectively putting brain cells at risk. This review will bring into light a lot of strategies that target ferroptosis, such as iron chelation, where deferoxamine is the most profound example, antioxidants like ferrostatins and vitamin E, and enzyme inhibitors involved in lipid metabolism. Apart from gene therapy, nanoparticle-based drug delivery also shows great promise in all the foregoing avenues that selectively target the ferroptosis pathways and improve drug delivery across the blood-brain barrier. These strategies are promising for neuroprotection; however, a challenge exists in terms of drug specificity, off-target effects, and limited clinical trials. Future research is required to navigate these therapeutic strategies for actual clinical application. The role of ferroptosis during ischemic stroke and therapeutic interventions directed at it can lead to the introduction of appointments to clinical practice that accelerate the recoveries and outcomes of patient care.

Keywords: Ischemic stroke, ferroptosis inhibitors, iron chelation, oxidative stress, lipid peroxidation, neuroprotection.

Graphical Abstract:

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

INTRODUCTION

Stroke is a medical condition that occurs when there is inadequate blood supply to the brain, either due to blockage, also known as "ischemic stroke", or bleeding, or "haemorrhagic stroke" [1]. This cutting off of blood supply is where brain cells do not receive oxygen and nutrients. This can in turn kill the brain cells and subsequently lead to permanent impairment or disabilities, such as paralysis, inability to speak, and cognitive dysfunction [2]. Stroke remains the second leading cause of death and the third leading cause of disability worldwide. In 2016, around 13.7 million new cases of stroke were reported around the world; 87% of them were ischemic strokes. The economic burden of stroke is considerable, amounting to an approximate total of \$721 billion in diverse costs, which approximates 0.66% of the world GDP. In 2016, it was reported that the annual cost of stroke in the United States was upward of \$46 billion [3]. The greatest burden to stroke takes place in low- and middle-income countries, which comprise 86% of stroke deaths and 89% of disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) lost. Advances in medicine have found that fewer than 5% of patients with acute ischemic stroke receive intravenous thrombolysis (IVT), while fewer than 100,000 mechanical thrombectomies (MTs) were performed worldwide in 2016, [4] representing a huge gap in access to treatment. Stroke primarily affects older individuals but can occur at any age. Risk factors include high blood pressure, diabetes, smoking, obesity, and an unhealthy lifestyle. Immediate medical involvement is crucial to minimize brain damage [5]. The latest therapies in stroke management have included tPA (that is, the clot-busting chemical), mechanical thrombectomy, and emerging modalities like DM199 (synthetic protein therapy) and stem-cell-based products. Yet, access to these therapies is the greatest hurdle [6]. Hence, in controlling blood pressure, lifestyle assistance, and early detection are integral means to reduce mortality and disability from stroke records.

An ischemic stroke happens when the artery that delivers blood to the brain gets blocked, thus limiting oxygen and nutrients to the brain. As a result, cell death occurs because the brain relies on oxygen and glucose to function normally [7]. The blockage creates an imbalance of ions, increases the influx of

calcium, and causes excitotoxicity in other neurons from neurotransmitters like glutamate. Reduced oxygen also limits the production of ATP, thus creating oxidative stress that damages proteins, lipids, and DNA. Additionally, reperfusion injury, when blood flow is restored, can actually worsen oxidative stress [8]. There are several aspects of inflammation caused by the immune response. This contributes to secondary injury by breaking down the blood-brain barrier, allowing harmful substances to enter the brain. This can lead to cell death by apoptosis or necrosis. Neurogenesis and angiogenesis may occur later on as the brain attempts to repair itself, however intervention with clot-busting drugs or mechanical thrombectomy early on can limit the damage to brain tissue and improve patient outcomes. Early diagnosis is critical for maximizing recovery in the short- and long-term and minimizing disability [9].

While current stroke therapies can be somewhat successful, they have limitations. Thrombolytic therapy using alteplase (tPA) aims to break down the clot in the case of ischemic stroke patients with a narrow window of 3–5 hours from the onset of strokes for timely intervention, resultant outcomes typically regress with outcomes of severe morbidities or risk of death due to potential intracranial hemorrhage [10]. Not all patients will be able to have this intervention due to strict medical contraindications (e.g. past surgeries, bleeding disorders, high-risk bleeding issues). Compounding the complexity, many stroke patients arrive at hospitals too late to receive tPA. Mechanical thrombectomy extends the treatment window to 24 hours and is a very good option available for non-tPA candidates and is required to remove the clot from large vessels. Like tPA, its efficacy also depends on the qualified team and facility, such as an advanced stroke centre, as well as risks like vessel puncture, clot fragments that embolize, vessel occlusion, strokes, and hemorrhages [11]. After the acute phase, management aims to prevent recurrence and promote recovery.

Controlling high blood pressure is important, but it is complicated by the side effects of antihypertensive drugs that can include side effects such as dizziness, tiredness, and kidney dysfunction. Antithrombotic therapies, such as aspirin, are indicated for many patients; however, their bleeding effects may render

them inappropriate in some patients [12]. Even though rehabilitation therapies (such as physical and speech therapies) are important in the recovery process, many patients may still exhibit limited recovery despite active participation due to the irreversibility of the brain injury.

Despite advances in medicine and understanding, stroke remains one of the leading causes of long-term disability and death globally. One area of concern that continues to persist is ischemia/reperfusion injury, whereby blood flow restoration to the brain causes more long-term damage due to increased oxidative stress and inflammation. This highlights a lack of effective treatment methods and a clear need for alternative approaches. One of the most promising alternative treatments appears to be iron chelation therapy, which is based on targeting iron-mediated oxidative stress, which directly affects secondary damage to the neuron. Iron chelators may present a new approach to limit oxidative stress and increase neuroprotection.

2. FERROPTOSIS IN ISCHEMIC STROKE

Ferroptosis is an iron-dependent form of regulated cell death that involves lipid peroxidation and oxidative stress. Ferroptosis was first described in 2012 by Dixon as another type of cell death that is protein distinct from apoptosis, necrosis, and autophagy in terms of morphological and biochemical characteristics [13]. The morphological organization of these cell types is markedly different from that of

apoptosis, which is characterized by chromatin condensation and cytoplasmic shrinkage, or necrosis, which is associated with swelling of the cell and rupture of the membrane. In contrast, with respect to the general appearance of the cell, it is characterized by shrunken mitochondria, increased mitochondrial membrane density, and loss of cristae [14]. Therapeutic inactivation based on ferroptosis has become important to iron-dependent diseases such as cancer, neurodegeneration, acute kidney injury, and ischemia-reperfusion injury.

Following cerebral ischemia, ferroptosis plays a major role in neuronal death in the course of ischemic stroke. When an artery in the brain is blocked by a blood clot, the neurons in the ischemic core are the first to die, while the cortical region-the surrounding area with reduced blood flow-is temporarily functionally alive, but these cells can be vulnerable to ferroptotic injury [15]. The interruption in blood supply induces metabolic stress, mitochondrial dysfunction, excitotoxicity, and inflammation, all accomplices to ferroptosis. One of the major drivers for ferroptotic cell death involves iron overload in cell death, which promotes superoxide production and peroxidation of lipid peroxides that lead to oxidative damage [16]. Other evidence suggests that iron overload in ischemic stroke is implicated in the process through which tau overexpression transpires and may support a connection between ferroptosis and neurodegeneration [17].

2.1 Molecular mechanism of ferroptosis:

Fig. 1: Molecular mechanism of ferroptosis

This diagram depicts the molecular pathways leading to ferroptosis. Key processes include iron metabolism via the transferrin receptor (TfR), lipid peroxidation catalyzed by ACSL4 and LPCAT3, and the role of glutathione peroxidase 4 (GPX4) in neutralizing oxidative damage. The imbalance in glutathione and accumulation of lipid hydroperoxides initiate ferroptosis, a regulated cell death mechanism.

(Abbreviations: Tf – Transferrin, Tf receptor – Transferrin receptor, Fe^{3+} – Ferric ion, Fe^{2+} – Ferrous ion, STEAP3 – Six Transmembrane Epithelial Antigen of the Prostate 3, DMT1 – Divalent Metal Transporter 1, NMDAR – N-Methyl-D-Aspartate Receptor, cPLA2 α – Cytosolic Phospholipase A2 alpha, AA – Arachidonic Acid, ACSL4 – Acyl-CoA Synthetase Long Chain Family Member 4, LPCAT3 – Lyso-phosphatidyl-choline Acyl-transferase 3, AA-PE – Arachidonic Acid-Phosphatidylethanolamine, AA-PE-OOH – Oxidized Arachidonic Acid-Phosphatidylethanolamine Hydroperoxide, SLC3A2 – Solute Carrier Family 3 Member 2, Glu – Glutamate, Cys – Cysteine, GPX4 – Glutathione Peroxidase 4). Detailed pathways link mechanisms of metabolic disruption induced by stroke to ferroptosis. The Glutathione Peroxidase 4 (GPX4) pathway is implicated in protecting neurons against ferroptotic damage by reducing lipid peroxides as shown in Fig. 1. Lipid peroxides build up upon reduced GPX4 activity due to ischemic conditions, gathering the way for ferroptosis and neuronal injury [18]. Similar is the Nuclear Factor Erythroid 2-Related Factor 2 (Nrf2) pathway acting as an important protective arm against oxidative stress modulation via antioxidant enzyme

expression. Current evidence implicates activation of a signaling pathway for Nrf2 to reverse injuries inflicted by ferroptosis [19]. Moreover, some non-coding RNAs (ncRNAs), like Plasmacytoma Variant Translocation 1 (PVT1), can promote ferroptosis through modulation of expression of iron metabolism genes like Transferrin Receptor 1 (TfR1) and p53. This molecular pathway gives insight into the targeting of ferroptosis-related pathways, which could be neuroprotective in the recovery following ischemic stroke [20]. Ferroptosis is a controlled type of cell death initiated by iron overload and lipid peroxidation, which is responsible for ischemic stroke-induced neuronal injury [21]. Stroke interferes with cerebral blood flow, causing metabolic stress, overproduction of reactive oxygen species (ROS), and mitochondrial damage [22]. This oxidative stress, exacerbated by iron overload, enhances phospholipid hydroperoxide (PL-OOH) accumulation, initiating ferroptosis as shown in Fig. 2. Regulators of importance are lipid metabolism enzymes, antioxidant defenses, and regulators of iron metabolism. Under normal circumstances, glutathione peroxidase 4 (GPX4) inhibits lipid peroxidation, but ischemia suppresses its activity, enhancing oxidative damage [23]. Simultaneously, iron homeostasis disruption characterized by elevated transferrin receptor 1 (TfR1) and decreased ferroportin magnifies ROS production through the Fenton reaction, causing mitochondrial condensation, cristae loss, and membrane rupture, distinguishing ferroptosis from apoptosis or necrosis as shown in following Fig. 2 [24].

This diagram illustrates the regulatory pathways linking stroke-induced cellular metabolism disruption to ferroptosis. Stroke generates reactive oxygen species (ROS) and alters iron (Fe) metabolism, leading to lipid peroxidation mediated by phospholipid hydroperoxides (PL-OOH). This cascade culminates in ferroptosis, a form of cell death with implications for physiological functions and therapeutic targeting in neuroprotection. The question mark (?) perhaps indicates doubt or ongoing investigations into the therapeutic potential of ferroptosis. The physiological functions of ferroptosis have been known for some time, but its modulation as a lessening-promoting or inhibitory therapeutic strategy is still a work in progress, particularly in conditions like cancer, neurodegeneration, and ischemia-reperfusion injury.

Iron chelators, antioxidants, and inhibitors of several enzymes have all been evaluated in preclinical and clinical studies as promising compounds to inhibit ferroptosis [25]. For example, Ferroptosis inhibition by iron chelators, lipid peroxides inhibitors, and antioxidants has shown potential to decrease neuronal damage and enhance recovery from stroke. These mechanisms may lead to new therapeutic strategies as follows:

2.2 Different Strategies for Ferroptosis inhibition:

2.2.1 Iron Chelation:

Iron chelators such as deferoxamine (DFO), deferiprone, and deferasirox are critical in reducing oxidative stress that is produced by free iron that fuels oxidative stress through the Fenton reaction that creates harmful reactive oxygen species (ROS) [26]. In pathologies like ischemic stroke, thalassemia, and sickle cell anaemia, iron overload has been implicated in causing neuronal damage through ferroptosis, an iron-dependent regulated cell death pathway characterized by lipid peroxidation. By sequestering excess labile iron, chelators can reduce the production of hydroxyl radicals and inhibit ferroptotic pathways [27]. DFO has neuroprotective properties by limiting infarct volume and preserving neuronal function when administered in stroke models. DFO and deferiprone cross the blood brain barrier and are highly effective in iron removal from the brain

whereas deferasirox has practical advantages in that it can be given orally and achieve a systemic reduction in iron. [28].

Iron chelators like deferoxamine (DFO), deferiprone, and deferasirox are vital for reversal of HL due to oxidative stress from free iron contributing to oxidative stress through the fenton reaction producing damaging reactive oxygen species (ROS) [29]. In diseases like ischemic stroke, thalassemia, and sickle cell anaemia, iron overload is thought to contribute to neuronal injury and death likely due to ferroptosis, an iron-dependent regulated mode of cell death noted for its lipid peroxidation. Iron chelators limit the labile iron, reduce hydroxyl radicals that induce ferroptotic pathways. DFO has neuroprotective significance by reducing the volume of infarction and preserving neuron function when given in animal stroke models [30]. DFO and deferiprone also penetrate the blood brain barrier and are effective in iron chelation in the brain although DFO is administered as an intravenous infusion. Deferasirox has other practical advantages of oral administration with reduction of systemic iron and easier long-term administration compared with parenteral iron chelators like DFO and deferiprone [31].

2.2.2 Antioxidant Therapy:

Antioxidant therapy has emerged as a promising and targeted approach to inhibit ferroptosis, a different type of regulated cell death characterized by iron-dependent lipid peroxidation. Central to ferroptosis is the build-up of reactive oxygen species (ROS), especially lipid hydroperoxides, as cellular antioxidant protection/balancing capacity fails. The System Xc⁻-glutathione (GSH) glutathione peroxidase 4 (GPX4) pathway is essential for reducing lipids ROS species and sustaining redox balance as a cellular process [32]. When this pathway becomes dysregulated, for example, by downregulating the cystine/glutamate antiporter (SLC7A11) transporter, or GSH depletion, lipid peroxides build-up leading to membrane disruption and cell death by ferroptosis. Antioxidants that trap radicals such as ferrostatin-1 (Fer-1) and liproxstatin-1 (Lip-1), can inhibit lipid peroxidation directly, and have shown neuroprotective effects in models of ischemia (low blood flow) and neurodegeneration

[33]. Vitamin E (α -tocopherol) is a small lipophilic anti-oxidant that also protects membrane integrity by quenching lipids radicals, and selenium enhances GPX4 activity providing anti-oxidant capacity at the cellular level. In addition, the transcription factor Nrf2 is a master regulator for the expression of many anti-oxidant and iron-related proteins (i.e. GPX4, SLC7A11, HO-1, ferritin) producing a link between redox signalling a suppression of ferroptosis [34].

In addition to the GPX4-GSH pathway, other antioxidant pathways include FSP1-CoQ10, DHODH-CoQH₂, GCH1-BH₄, and the transsulfuration pathway to lessen oxidative stress. These pathways produce stable and excellent reducing molecules like ubiquinol (CoQH₂) or tetrahydrobiopterin (BH₄) which stabilize membrane lipids against oxidative harm [35]. The role of oxidative stress in the context of ischemic injuries and neurodegenerative diseases is an essential consideration, and antioxidant treatments targeting ferroptosis have great potential for drug development. However, further research should explore dosing, delivery, and combinations with other neuroprotective agents to improve clinical safety and efficacy [36].

2.2.3 Ferroptosis-Related Enzyme Inhibitors:

Inhibitors of ferroptosis-related enzymes have emerged as an important therapeutic approach to mitigate damage caused by ferroptosis in a variety of pathologies, particularly in ischemia-related pathology and neurodegeneration [37]. Ferroptosis is a distinct iron-dependent regulated cell death characterized by the accumulation of iron and lipid peroxides in cell membranes. Some of the most studied drivers of ferroptosis include a number of enzymes: acyl-CoA synthetase long-chain family member 4 (ACSL4) and lipoxygenases (LOX). ACSL4 converts polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs) into their acyl-CoA configurations prior to lipid peroxidation and the LOX proteins directly mediate the peroxidation of PUFAs into lipid hydroperoxides [38]. Peroxidation damages membranes and leads to ferroptotic death. By inhibiting the activity of these shared ferroptosis-dependent enzymes, inhibitors have emerged as a promising neuroprotective strategy. Use of ACSL4 inhibitors (e.g.

thiazolidinediones) and LOX inhibitors (e.g. zileuton) have been helpful to reduce lipid peroxidation, decrease infarct volume, and improve outcomes in neuroprotection preclinical studies of ischemia models. The specific enzyme inhibitors disrupt the sequelae of ferroptosis while also preserving the membrane and avoiding neuronal death after the injury caused by oxidation. Enzyme inhibitors with this unique mode of action targeting major drivers of ferroptosis make them particularly attractive for neuroprotective strategies [39]. However, even with these advances, it is important to further explore their long-term impacts, potential off-target effects, and overall safety profiles in a clinical setting. Future studies should also focus on the optimization of these drugs' pharmacokinetics and further assess their selectivity and the potential combination of these drugs with other ferroptosis regulators for additive effects. [40].

2.2.4 Glutathione Metabolism Modulation:

Modulating glutathione (GSH) metabolism has become a paramount therapeutic focus in targeting ferroptosis, especially in conditions of oxidative stress such as ischemic injury. GSH is the major intracellular antioxidant, crucial for neutralizing lipid peroxides and maintaining cellular redox balance. Glutathione peroxidase 4 (GPX4) is an important executor of ferroptosis, using GSH to convert reactive lipid hydroperoxides into non-reactive lipid alcohols. When intracellular GSH is depleted, GPX4 loses activity leading to accumulation of lipid peroxides which subsequently leads to ferroptotic cell death. Increasing GSH biosynthesis has been found to provide protection against ferroptosis [41]. Compounds such as N-acetylcysteine (NAC) and other cysteine donors (as precursors of GSH biosynthesis), has been shown to provide cellular GSH pool replenishment, GPX4 activity, and ferroptosis protection. Furthermore, induction of the expression or activity of glutamate-cysteine ligase (GCL), the rate limiting enzyme in GSH biosynthesis, may better increase intracellular GSH levels as well [42]. This has particular relevance in ischemic stroke and neurodegenerative disorders where oxidative stress and redox imbalance further exacerbates neuronal damage. When intracellular GSH levels drop, GPX4 becomes inactive, leading to the

accumulation of toxic lipid peroxides and the onset of ferroptosis. Enhancing GSH synthesis through precursors such as N-acetylcysteine (NAC) or supplementation with cysteine donors can help restore its levels and prevent cell death [43]. Additionally, drugs that upregulate glutamate-cysteine ligase (GCL), the key enzyme in GSH biosynthesis, offer therapeutic potential. Maintaining acceptable GSH levels is crucial in ischemic conditions, where oxidative stress is a significant driver of neuronal injury.

2.2.5 Targeting Ferroptosis Pathways via Gene Therapy:

One intriguing method for directly modifying ferroptosis-related pathways at the genetic level is gene therapy. RNA interference (RNAi) and CRISPR-Cas9 methods can either increase the expression of protective genes like GPX4 or specifically mute genes linked to lipid peroxidation, such as ACSL4 [44]. By precisely targeting these genes, it is possible to reduce susceptibility to ferroptosis and enhance neuronal survival following ischemic injury. Additionally, viral and non-viral vectors can be used to carry gene-editing tools to affected tissues, offering a potential long-term solution for ischemia-induced ferroptosis [45]. Despite its potential, gene therapy faces several challenges, including off-target effects, immune responses, and the difficulty of efficiently delivering genetic material to target cells. Further research is needed to improve these techniques for clinical application [46].

All of the above total 5 methods are explained to overcome ferroptosis. In this review article we focused first method i.e. iron chelation method.

Ferroptosis is a form of regulated cell death controlled by iron-dependent lipid peroxidation. Iron chelators, which reduce the availability of free iron by binding to it, is one of the approaches to overcome ferroptosis cross-link with, and increase the availability of, the Fenton reaction, a major participant in lipid peroxidation as shown in Fig. 1 [47]. Common iron chelators like deferoxamine (DFO), deferiprone (DFP), and deferasirox (DFX) are in this regard. These agents sequester excess intracellular iron, thus reducing oxidative stress and avoiding buildup of reactive oxygen species (ROS) that induce ferroptotic

pathways [48]. Additionally, iron chelators can disrupt the supply of iron necessary for enzymes like lipoxygenases, further inhibiting lipid peroxidation. In therapeutic applications, combining iron chelators with antioxidants such as glutathione or inhibitors of lipid peroxidation, like ferrostatins, enhances their efficacy [49]. This dual approach not only stabilizes cellular redox balance but also preserves membrane integrity, offering a promising strategy for diseases where ferroptosis plays a pathogenic role, such as neurodegenerative disorders, cancer, and ischemia-reperfusion injuries.

3. OXIDATIVE STRESS AND INFLAMMATION

When an ischemic stroke occurs, it disrupts the brain's natural balance of reactive oxygen species (ROS) molecules that can be harmful in excess but are normally regulated by the body's antioxidant defenses. Under normal conditions, ROS play a role in cell signaling and homeostasis, but during a stroke, their production increases uncontrollably due to a lack of oxygen and nutrients [50]. This imbalance leads to oxidative stress, a condition where excessive ROS begin damaging essential cell components like proteins, lipids, and DNA. As a result, brain cells experience severe inflammation and structural damage, leading to cell death [51]. The brain tissue becomes even more vulnerable due to a process called lipid peroxidation, in which ROS target the lipids in cell membranes. Furthermore, mitochondrial malfunction takes place, which lowers the cell's capacity to produce energy and exacerbates neuronal damage. In extreme situations, oxidative stress plays a role in the breakdown of the blood-brain barrier, which permits toxic substances and immune cells to enter the brain. This increases inflammation and exacerbates the severity of stroke [52]. To counter these harmful effects, the body activates antioxidant enzymes like superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase, and glutathione peroxidase (GPX) to neutralize ROS. However, in stroke conditions, these defenses are often overcome, making medical interventions like iron chelators, antioxidants, and enzyme inhibitors crucial in reducing brain damage. Understanding and controlling oxidative stress is key to developing better treatments that protect brain cells and improve recovery after an ischemic stroke [53].

3.1 Inflammation and the Ferroptosis-Oxidative Stress Axis:

The roles of inflammation, oxidative stress, and ferroptosis are related in the pathophysiology of multiple diseases, with ischemic stroke being the most prominent example. Inflammation has a dual nature; it is critical for repairing damaged tissues and clearing debris from dead cells, but prolonged and/or excessive inflammation can worsen neuronal damage leading to worsen stroke outcomes, in part due to ferroptosis [54]. Ferroptosis is an iron-dependent, regulated form of cell death associated with the destabilization of the cell membrane from lipid peroxidation. The oxidation/reduction state of the cell can be a significant contributor to inflammation and the ferroptosis-oxidative stress focuses on elevate inflammatory signal, and elevated levels of reactive oxygen species (ROS) from the depletion of antioxidant defenses (glutathione (GSH), GPX4 and SOD) as well as activation of ferroptosis [55]. Yu et al. (2024) demonstrated with their study with DBDPE and PS-NPs, that environmental contaminants induced oxidative stress and ferroptosis in the grass carp hepatocytes via dysregulation of iron homeostasis in cooperating with identified proinflammatory cytokines (IL-6, IL-1 β , TNF- α). The group also emphasizes that if exposed to both DBDPE and PS-NPs simultaneously, the levels of ROS, Fe²⁺ and inflammatory mediators are synergistically Elevated [56]. Overall, this study offers evidence of oxidative stress and ferroptosis driving inflammation together, where the DBDPE and PS-NPs drive the ferroptosis-oxidative stress-inflammation feedback loop in the grass carp model. The study highlights features reported with ischemic stroke including oxidative damage from iron overload and neuroinflammation that will upregulate ferroptotic signaling pathway even further [57]. The study also showed that ferrostatin-1, a ferroptosis inhibitor, ameliorated these effects, suggesting a potential and therapeutic avenue for modulating this axis. Collectively, our results highlight the importance of targeting and modulating the inflammation ferroptosis oxidative stress axis as a pathogenic pathway to mitigate neurodegeneration and tissue damage post-ischemic stroke, and further related conditions.

3.2 Inflammatory Signaling Molecules:

Cytokines and chemokines are important inflammatory signaling molecules that control the body's defense response to potentially damaging stimuli (like microbial pathogens, toxins, and physical injury). Inflammation pathways mediated by these signaling molecules regulate the activation and recruitment of immune cells, particularly monocytes, macrophages, neutrophils, dendritic cells, mast cells, T-cells, and B-cells to the site of injury [58]. The major physical symptoms of inflammation redness, swelling, heat, pain, and loss of function are the end-products of the inflammatory molecular and cellular response. Cytokines (such as tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α), interleukin-1 beta (IL-1 β), and interleukin-6 (IL-6)) are significant mediators of both acute and chronic inflammation. These various cytokines are released in an acute stroke occurring after ischemia and enhance immune responses; however, when produced in excess, these cytokines can have adverse effects, including promoting oxidative stress and ferroptosis instead [59]. In particular, in some cases, cytokines can increase the expression of genes that regulate ferroptosis and promote lipid peroxidation, leading to neuronal death. In addition, some chemokines (for example, interleukin-8 (IL-8)) signal through G protein-coupled receptors (GPCRs) and regulate the recruitment of neutrophils and microglia, thereby further increasing reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation and leading to ferroptotic death [60]. This interaction creates a cycle of inflammation, oxidative stress and ferroptosis that exacerbate the extent of tissue damage. A full appreciation of the complicate roles of signaling molecules involved in inflammation has been significant in repositioning many diseases from coronary heart disease, Alzheimer's disease, diabetes and obesity to being interpreted as inflammatory diseases [61]. Therefore, targeting specific cytokines and the signaling pathways they produce, offer therapeutic approaches for managing inflammation and thus reversing ferroptosis-induced diseases, in particular neurological and autoimmune diseases [62].

3.3 Iron Release and Its Role in Ferroptosis:

The release of iron is central to initiating and driving the regulated cell death of ferroptosis, which is associated with iron dependent lipid peroxidation.

Under physiological conditions, iron is safely sequestered in cells bound to ferritin, which protects them from engaging in deleterious redox reactions [63]. However, when pathological conditions occur such as ischemic stroke, damaged brain tissue and activated immune cells release free iron overwhelming the cellular sod. Free iron then catalyzes hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) to a highly reactive hydroxyl radicals (OH·) through a Fenton reaction, immensely elevating oxidative stress and causing further injury to cells. Additionally, iron contributes to iron dysregulation through reduced ferritin expression, further increasing the susceptibility of neurons to damage from iron-dependent oxidative insult [64]. This free iron sharply reduces cellular redox homeostasis, which accelerates lipid peroxidation; thiol peroxidation is the point of no return promoting cell death through ferroptosis. Given that the release of iron serves as a common hub for oxidative stress, inflammation and cell death pathways; targeting iron as a therapeutic for lessening quality loss of ferroptotic neurons prevents neuronal death during ischemic stroke [65].

3.4 Oxidative Stress Amplification and Ferroptosis Progression:

Inflammation and oxidative stress are intimately interrelated, one fuelling the other. As inflammatory cells enter stroke-injured tissues, they produce

copious amounts of reactive oxygen species (ROS), such as superoxide (O₂•⁻) and hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) [66]. ROS inflict substantial damage to neuronal membranes by oxidizing polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs), which are prevalent in brain cells. This process, termed lipid peroxidation, is a characteristic of ferroptosis [67]. Furthermore, glutathione (GSH), the key antioxidant in the brain, is depleted, weakening the cell's capacity to neutralize ROS. With the antioxidant defense mechanism weakened, neurons become susceptible to ferroptosis, resulting in irreversible cell death and exacerbation of stroke outcomes as indicated in Fig. 2 [68].

The relationship between ferroptosis and inflammation in ischemic stroke underscores the importance of therapy targeting these phenomena. Although inflammation is required for healing, extended inflammation induces iron dysregulation and overproduced oxidative stress, eventually inducing ferroptotic cell death [69]. It is possible that by treating it with drugs regulating inflammation, maintaining iron homeostasis, and boosting antioxidant mechanisms, neuronal damage can be prevented and stroke outcomes of recovery are enhanced.

4. Evidence from preclinical and clinical studies of ferroptosis in ischemic stroke:

Table 1: Preclinical Studies: Insights from Cell Culture and Animal Models

Topic	Key Finding	Reference(s)	Model Type	Subjects
Ferroptosis Inhibitors	Ferrostatin-1, liproxstatin-1 reduce infarct size, oxidative stress	[70], [71]	In vivo & in vitro	Rodents (mouse stroke models), neuron cultures
Microglia Activation	Microglia exacerbate ferroptosis via cytokine release	[72], [73]	In vivo	Rodent ischemic stroke models
Glial Cell Ferroptosis	Astrocyte/oligodendrocyte death disrupts BBB via ferroptosis	[74], [75], [76]	In vivo & in vitro	Rodent glial cultures & models
Mitochondrial Role	Mitochondrial dysfunction leads to ROS accumulation and ferroptosis	[77], [78]	In vivo	Rodents; primary neural cells
Oxidative Stress Mechanisms	4-HNE, MDA involved in ferroptosis pathways	[79], [80]	In vivo & in vitro	Rodents; neuronal cells
Therapeutic Targets	Early tests of vitamin E, ferrostatin-1, nanomedicine strategies	[81], [82]	In vivo	Rodent ischemic stroke models

Table 2: Clinical Studies & Trials on Ferroptosis-Linked Mechanisms in Stroke

Topic	Key Finding	Reference(s)	Study Type	Subjects	Clinical Trial Info
Serum Ferritin	High ferritin correlates with poor stroke outcome	[82]	Observational	Human stroke patients	Not interventional
Iron Accumulation (MRI)	MRI reveals iron deposition in ischemic regions	[83], [84]	Imaging-based clinical study	Stroke patients	Used for diagnostic/monitoring purposes
Iron Chelation	Deferoxamine reduces damage post-stroke	[85]	Clinical trial (Phase I/II)	Stroke patients	Trial ID: NCT02175225
Oxidative Stress Markers	MDA, 4-HNE linked with infarct size and severity	[86]	Biomarker study	Ischemic stroke patients	Correlative, not therapeutic
Antioxidant Therapeutics	N-acetyl serotonin, vitamin E show promise	[87], [88]	Translational / exploratory	Small clinical cohorts	Trials in early phase or under proposal
Mesenchymal Cell Therapy	MSCs modulate ferroptosis-related inflammation	[89]	Ongoing clinical trials	Human subjects	Numerous trials (e.g., NCT03305037)
Nanomedicine & Drug Delivery	Ferroptosis-targeted nano therapies under development	[90]	Preclinical transitioning to clinical	No large-scale human data yet	Investigational/ New Drug (IND) stage

5. Ferroptosis Inhibitors

There are different iron chelators as a Ferroptosis Inhibitors:

5.1. The effect of DP (2,2'-dipyridyl) on ischemia-induced damage to endothelial and neuronal cells:

The relative iron chelator 2, 2'-dipyridyl (DP) has been demonstrated to possess ferroptosis inhibitor capability and has a protective effect against ischemia-induced damage in endothelial and neuronal cells [91]. Specifically, protection of endothelial cells DP treatment has greatly minimized the vascular leakage due to ischemia. Mainly, extravasation of EB was clearly seen in the samples without DP treatment than those with DP treatment. This suggests that the endarterial lining is not compromised by ischemia [92]. Neuroprotection this study assesses that the DP treatment brought a significant improvement in the parameters that described the extent of neuronal loss, reflected by the reduction of both the infarct volume and the maximal infarct area. Such effects underpin this as a protective agent against ischemia induced neuronal damage [93]. Preservation of Neuronal Health i.e. N-acetyl aspartate (NAA) level, DP

treatment also reduced the reductions in NAA, a marker of neuronal health and functioning, following ischemia. A marked preservation of the levels of NAA was evident in areas in which ischemia resulted in its decrease possibly indicating that DP contributes to the support of neuronal metabolic activity during ischemic insult [94]. Taken together, these data indicate that DP is effective in preventing ferroptosis and minimizing the ischemia-mediated injury of vessels and neurons.

5.2 Effect of DP on Ischemic - Stimulated ROS Formation:

2,2'-Dipyridyl (DP) is an established iron chelator that has demonstrated significant protective effects against ischemia associated oxidative stress through modulating levels of reactive oxygen species (ROS) [95]. During an ischemic event (myocardial infarction, stroke, etc.), there is a rapid decrease and re-introduction of oxygen availability, leading to a burst of ROS formation predominantly from mitochondria as well as NADPH oxidase and other enzyme systems found in the endothelial and cardiac tissues. Free iron worsens this problem by catalyzing the Fenton reaction to produce reactive hydroxyl

radicals (OH•) which induce lipid peroxidation and cellular injury [96]. DP chelates free iron, thereby effectively limiting iron induced ROS production and oxidative stress. Based on studies conducted using ischemic heart and brain tissue, treatment with DP significantly reduced depletion of intracellular antioxidants (e.g., glutathione [GSH]) during oxidative stress when GSH is consumed to neutralize ROS [97]. In addition, in the ischemic-affected cortical areas, DP inhibited ROS overproduction and furthermore, retained activities of antioxidant enzymes, supporting its localization in maintaining redox homeostasis. Perhaps most interestingly, in the minimally ischemic affected tissue areas, DP showed little-to-no change in oxidative markers, suggesting its mechanism of action is mostly localized to the regions of ischemic damage and inflammation. These data support DP's ability to attenuate ischemia-induced ROS formation, and suggest a potential therapeutic role for DP in diseases with a known oxidative damage component to their pathophysiology [98], [99].

5.3 Activation and Fe-chelating activity of BHAPI (Bipyridyl-Hydroxy-Aromatic Pyridyl Intermediate)

The structure of BHAPI is also presented here. In order to determine the stability of BHAPI and HAPI in our in vitro model, BHAPI and HAPI, both at 100M, were added into culture medium, or culture medium containing the control cells or glutamate-treated cells, and the sample was taken 24 hours later for HPLC analysis [100]. When glutamate was absent, the detectable concentrations of BHAPI and HAPI declined to somewhat comparable levels and HAPI ending from BHAPI did not increase up to 12 hours. Glutamate significantly decreased the level of BHAPI and HAPI: the complete cleavage of BHAPI into HAPI was determined after 24 hrs. For the measurement of the iron binding capacity, this work also employed the calcein-AM assay [101], [102]. Altogether, the results pointed out that BHAPI failed to bind iron individually, and both HAPI and the glutamate cured BHAPI enhanced the fluorescence intensity substantially.

5.4 Deferoxamine (DFO):

Deferoxamine (DFO) is an iron chelator that is FDA-approved and high-affinity, and is already noted for its role as an inhibitor of ferroptosis through the chelation of excess free iron with subsequent prevention of iron-mediated redox reactions [103]. Ferroptosis is an iron-dependent form of cell death driven by lipid peroxidation that can contribute to critical pathological processes in several disease states including: spinal cord injury, stroke, osteoarthritis, and cancer. Deferoxamine serves as a "chelator" of free Fe²⁺ and Fe³⁺ ions to limit the generation of highly reactive hydroxyl radicals through the Fenton reaction, promoting a reduction in oxidative stress, as well as cellular integrity [104]. In spinal cord injury models, treatment with DFO via intraperitoneal inject not only inhibited mitochondrial shrinkage while preventing iron overload, but also promoted locomotor recovery and increased expression of anti-ferroptotic markers GPX4 and xCT. Likewise, in ischemic stroke models, DFO administered intranasally reduced total infarct volume up to 55%, signifying that DFO exhibits neuroprotective properties via inhibition of iron-mediated oxidative injury [105]. Of note, a recent study showed DFO inhibited the progression of osteoarthritis, by inhibiting chondrocyte ferroptosis and stimulating the Nrf2 antioxidant pathway as well as reducing ROS accumulation, lipid peroxidation, and extracellular matrix degeneration. DFO also inhibits pro-ferroptotic proteins such as ACSL4, LOX15, and P53 and highlights DFO's global role. Combined, these findings confer DFO as a potent inhibitor against ferroptosis and a promising therapeutic option for diseases caused by oxidative stress and iron dysregulation [106], [107]. Research continues to improve clinical usages of DFO by optimizing delivery mechanisms, dosing regimens, and side effects.

5.5 Natural Compounds with Ferroptosis Inhibitory Properties:

Ferroptosis is a form of regulated cell death driven by iron-dependent lipid peroxidation. While research into ferroptosis is still ongoing, it has gained interest as a potential target for cancer therapy. Several natural compounds have been shown in Table 1 to inhibit ferroptosis, including:

Table 3: Natural Compounds and Their Role in Ferroptosis Inhibition

Sr. no	Compounds	Active Constituents	Pharmaceutical Preparations / Dosage Forms	Benefits	References
1.	Turmeric - Rhizome of the turmeric plant (native to India and Southeast Asia)	Curcumin (a polyphenol with antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activity)	- Capsules/tablets (e.g., Curcumin C3 Complex, Meriva) - Injectable forms (in clinical trials) - Liposomal/nano formulations for enhanced absorption	Ferroptosis is suppressed via antioxidant systems' modulation and iron metabolism processes' balance among various pathways.	[108]
2.	Spinach - Leafy green vegetable	Dihydrolipoic acid, Lutein, zeaxanthin, folate, iron, vitamin E, alpha-lipoic acid	- Capsules/tablets as dietary supplements (e.g., spinach extract) - Often used in multi-vitamin and iron-rich supplements	Ferroptosis is also inhibited in this context by scavenging free radicals with high specificity and thereby preventing oxidative damage.	[109], [110]
3.	Broccoli - Edible green flowering plant (Cruciferous vegetable family)	Sulforaphane, indole-3-carbinol, vitamin C, fiber	- Sulforaphane supplements (capsules, tablets) - Standardized broccoli sprout extract (e.g., BrocElite, Avmacol) - Functional foods and juices	Ferroptosis is distinguished by lipid peroxidation, a hallmark of the condition, and this substance is an established antioxidant that suppresses this process.	[111]

The fact that the research about the use of these natural compounds as ferroptosis inhibitors is still at the initial stage should be remembered. More studies are required to determine the safety and efficiency of the drugs in humans. The ways in which these drugs exhibit their death-subduing effects may differ. It is possible that these might best suit the type of cancer cells they face the most successfully. Natural components may have other health benefits besides having the main action to prevent ferroptosis [112].

6. NANOPARTICLE-BASED STRATEGIES

Nanoparticles (NPs) can be applied in ferroptosis-based cancer therapy in various ways:

6.1 Transporting ferrotherapeutics:

NPs may serve as carriers to the desired site in cancerous cells for ferrotherapy, either through improved permeation or retention, or by active targeting which is site-directed. Ferrotherapy is an emerging branch of nanomedicine that uses magnetic nanomaterial for medical purposes [113], [114].

These nanoparticles can be delivered to the specific part of the body which is affected and manipulated by an external magnetic field. There are two possible mechanisms of ferrotherapy delivery that are Passive targeting: In this method, the nanoparticles get injected into the bloodstream and move through the entire body. The nano-sized particles are designed to dynamically collect in tumors or in injured tissue based on the high permeability and retention (EPR) effect [115]. The EPR effect is a concept used to refer to the permeable blood vessels of the tumors, which make it easy for the nanoparticles to traverse more easily than normal tissues. Active targeting: In this case, the nanoparticles are targeted with target-specific molecules which can target diseased cells. These molecules can be in the form of an antibody, peptide, or any other ligand specific to particular receptors on the surface of an infected cell [116].

6.2 Magnetic nanoparticles (NPs):

Magnetic Nanoparticles (MNPs), especially when leveraging ferroptosis in cancer therapy and/or enhancing diagnostic imaging, represent a robust

methodology for biomedical uses. Magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs), normally composed of iron oxides (Fe_3O_4 or $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$), can be used to accurately localize a delivery mechanism because of their superparamagnetic properties under external localized magnetic fields and as a magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) contrast agent [117]. MNPs can induce ferroptosis by releasing ferrous (Fe^{2+}) and ferric (Fe^{3+}) ions into acidic environments, such as lysosome, and catalyzing the Fenton reaction to produce reactive oxygen species (ROS) [118]. This ROS surge then drives lipids into peroxidation, the mechanism of ferroptotic cell death. Using targeting ligands to functionalize MNPs can promote selective accumulation into tumors, allowing for targeted delivery of therapeutic mechanisms localized specifically in that tumor site, with minimal invasiveness. New nanoparticles, such as ultrasmall single-crystal iron nanoparticles or engineered magnetosomes, provide better delivery and ease of increasing intracellular iron for MNP strategies, and with real-time MRI monitoring of therapeutic needs [119]. Magnetic fields not only attract these NPs to tumors but also initiate a controlled release of iron ions that can enhance the production of intracellular ROS. Beyond inducing ferroptosis directly, magnetic NPs are under development for dual drug cancer therapies matching ferroptosis to existing chemotherapy or immunotherapy, an innovative approach that promises to effectively address cancer's resistance to apoptosis. [120]. While these advances are encouraging, assuring biocompatibility, limiting toxicity, and achieving accurate control over NP distribution are still critical barriers that need to be overcome for the successful implementation of magnetic nanoparticle ferroptosis therapies in a clinical setting [121].

6.3 Combination of therapeutic agents:

NPs can combine multiple therapeutic agents thereby allowing for a synergistic approach to induce ferroptosis together with other kinds of cell death. Therapeutic agent combination for ferroptosis is one of the promising approaches for cancer therapy [122]. Ferroptosis is a regulated form of cell death that depends on iron and is different from apoptosis and necrosis. It is marked by the accumulation of lipid peroxides, which are toxic by-products of iron-

mediated oxidative stress. Nanoparticle-based approaches are being designed to deliver therapeutic agents that can activate ferroptosis in cancer cells.

There are essentially two approaches to combining therapeutic agents for ferroptosis:

6.3.1 Combining drugs that target different ferroptosis pathways:

Ferroptosis is a regulated form of cell death driven by iron-dependent lipid peroxidation and has emerged as a promising therapeutic target for cancer and other diseases. However, single-agent ferroptosis-inducing drugs often face resistance due to adaptive cellular mechanisms [123]. To address this problem, the combination of drugs targeting distinct ferroptosis pathways has been suggested as a powerful strategy to maximize treatment efficacy. Targeting both the cystine import system (SLC7A11) and glutathione peroxidase 4 (GPX4) is one such major strategy. SLC7A11, which is part of system Xc⁻, is the transporter that imports cystine into the cell, where it is reduced to cysteine and utilized for the synthesis of glutathione (GSH). GPX4, on the other hand, uses GSH to detoxify lipid peroxides and inhibit ferroptosis. Inhibition of SLC7A11 with drugs such as erastin decreases cystine uptake, which results in GSH depletion and enhanced oxidative stress. At the same time, inhibition of GPX4 by compounds such as RSL3 or ML162 inhibits detoxification of lipid peroxides, inducing ferroptosis [124]. The combination of these inhibitors has a synergistic effect by restricting GSH synthesis as well as lipid peroxide detoxification, thereby increasing ferroptotic cell death. In addition, combination therapy is a successful method to overcome drug resistance since tumors tend to develop adaptive resistance to single-agent ferroptosis inducers. By targeting multiple ferroptosis pathways simultaneously, combination therapy reduces adaptive resistance and provides a stronger and more effective treatment regimen [125].

6.3.2 Utilization of nanoparticles to deliver a combination of therapeutic agents:

Nanotechnology boosts ferroptosis therapy through better drug delivery, lowered systemic toxicity, and improved tumor targeting. Nanoparticles can deliver a combination of multiple drugs, including an

SLC7A11 inhibitor and a GPX4 inhibitor, allowing for coordinated release for optimal therapeutic synergy [126]. They also enable siRNA-induced gene silencing to combat ferroptosis resistance through the inhibition of protective genes such as GPX4 or NRF2. Functionalized nanoparticles with tumor-targeting ligands (e.g., folic acid, transferrin) increase drug entry into cancer cells and reduce toxicity to normal tissues. Nanoparticles also increase the solubility and stability of ferroptosis-inducing drugs and ensure long-term therapeutic effects [127].

Different nanoparticle types offer unique advantages: lipid-based nanoparticles (e.g., liposomes, micelles) encapsulate hydrophobic ferroptosis inducers, iron-based nanoparticles increase intracellular iron to promote lipid peroxidation, and polymeric/inorganic

nanoparticles enable controlled drug release [128]. Clinically, these approaches are promising for treating aggressive cancers like triple-negative breast cancer and glioblastoma, as well as neurodegenerative diseases where ferroptosis modulation can prevent oxidative damage. Nanoparticles can also be used in combination therapy, co-delivering ferroptosis inducers with chemotherapy or immunotherapy to enhance tumor eradication [129]. Nanoparticle-mediated approaches hold certain benefits for treating ferroptosis. Nanoparticles can enhance the delivery of therapeutic agents into tumor cells, minimize systemic side effects, and potentiate the drugs [130].

Here are some of the different types of nanoparticles that are being developed for ferroptosis therapy shown in Table 2:

Table 4: Types of Nanoparticles and Their Therapeutic Applications

Sr. no.	Types of Nanoparticles	Description	References
1.	Liposomes: Smaller sizes (100–200 nm) are ideal for tumor targeting due to enhanced permeability and retention (EPR) effect.	Phospholipids can be used to create spherical vesicles known as liposomes. The delivery of hydrophobic drugs to tumor cells can be achieved through encapsulation.	[131], [132]
2.	Polymeric nanoparticles: Size range is commonly 100–300 nm for biomedical use. Their size affects biodistribution, cellular uptake, and release kinetics of therapeutic agents.	Polymeric nanoparticles are composed of synthetic polymers. What are they made of?... They are capable of delivering therapeutic agents, including drugs, siRNAs, and imaging agents. Additional examples are available.	[133], [134]
3.	Metal nanoparticles: Size Range ~1 nm to 100 nm. Includes nanoparticles made from iron oxide, gold, silver, etc. For ROS generation and potential ferroptosis applications	Reactive oxygen species (ROS) can be generated through the use of metal nanoparticles, such as iron oxide nanostructured X-rays. Despite the lack of progress in nanoparticle-based ferroptosis therapy, they have the potential to revolutionize cancer treatment.	[135]

6.4 Targeting tumors:

In some cancers, blocking ferroptosis may actually help tumor cells survive under stressful conditions like oxidative stress or lack of nutrients. Tumors that have developed means of evading ferroptosis can become more resistant to standard treatments like chemotherapy or radiation [136]. Thus, targeting these mechanisms may render tumors more susceptible to ferroptosis, improving the likelihood of successful treatment. GPX4 Inhibitors are the

inhibitors targets GPX4, generating elevated lipid peroxidation as well as ferroptosis within cancer cells. This therapeutic method may work exceptionally well against cancer cells which rely significantly upon GPX4 for their endurance [137]. In Iron Modulation drugs that raise free iron levels in tumor cells are capable of triggering ferroptosis. These include drugs interfering with iron sequestration or boosting iron uptake. System Xc- (Cystine/Glutamate Antiporter) Inhibitors, by suppressing the cystine/glutamate antiporter, these compounds reduce glutathione

synthesis, leaving cells vulnerable to ferroptosis [138]. Lipid Peroxidation Inducers: Altered lipid metabolism in cancer cells to increase the pool of polyunsaturated fatty acids can induce ferroptosis. Targeting mechanisms by which tumors resist ferroptosis may enable the development of novel cancer therapies that improve tumor cell death and subsequent treatment efficacy [139].

6.5 Iron-based NPs:

Iron-based nanoparticles (NPs) are also a new alternative in neurodegenerative diseases and cancer therapy, with potential insertion of external iron into target cells. Through their further downregulation of iron homeostasis in tumor or injured cells, iron-based nanoparticles induce cytotoxicity by enhancing oxidative stress and cell death through ferroptosis [140]. Since the majority of tumors and disease tissues rely considerably on iron, iron-based NPs can serve as a targeted and efficient strategy for treatment. However, this kind of delivery has some difficulties to be accomplished in clinical scenarios. Iron is extremely toxic alone when it becomes excessively accumulated due to the fact that it destroys not only cancer cells but also the adjacent normal tissues [141]. Iron overload can interfere with cellular homeostasis and cause inflammation and mitochondrial dysfunction, as well as unwanted oxidative stress. The release rate of iron from nanoparticles should thus be tightly regulated to prevent increased cytotoxicity.

For enhancing the safety and efficiency of NPs, biodegradable and responsive formulation of nanoparticles have gained widespread attention. The new formulations facilitate controlled release of iron in a manner that allows one to minimize toxicity while allowing therapy [142]. Furthermore, specific targeting ligands like tumor-specific antibodies or peptide ligands efficiently bring iron to diseased cells while limiting off-target effects. Despite these difficulties, iron nanoparticles show great promise for designed and targeted methods of ferrotherapy. Current research focuses on buffering their basis for dosaging and targeting options in an effort to enable therapeutic effects while maintaining side effects within potential clinical use [143].

Advantages of Iron-Based Nanoparticles:

- **Biocompatibility:** Iron oxide nanoparticles tend to get accepted very well inside the body and can be metabolized or excreted without harming it significantly [144].
- **Versatility:** They can be employed for various therapeutic approaches-from direct destruction of tumors to targeted drug delivery [145].
- **Multimodal:** Iron-based nanoparticles can be co-administrated with other therapies like chemotherapy, radiotherapy, and immunotherapy to render the overall treatment much more effective [146].

7. CHALLENGES AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Table 5: Challenges and Future Directions in Ferroptosis Research

Sr. No.	Factors	Challenges	Future Directions
1.	Markers	Ferroptosis' identification is complicated because it lacks markers similar to apoptose and autophagy [147].	Determine the specific markers that can differentiate ferroptosis from other cell deaths.
2.	Mechanisms	However, the exact pathways of iron metabolism and lipid peroxidation in ferroptosis are unclear [148].	Describe the exact molecular mechanisms between iron metabolism, lipid peroxidation and ferroptosis.
3.	Iron Metabolism Proteins	There is uncertainty about the function of proteins such as TfR1, DMT1, and ferroportin	Explore the role of proteins such as TfR1, DMT1, and ferroportin 1 in various signalling pathways.

		1 in both ferroptosis and other pathways [149].	
4.	Role of Other Metals:	It is important to explore the role of metal ions other than iron in catabolic fermentation, including their involvement in ferroptosis [150].	Explore the ways in which other metal ions can induce ferroptosis.
5.	Cell-Type	It is not known how ferroptosis contribute to the function of several brain cell types (neurons, microglia, astrocytes, and oligodendrocyte) [151].	Evaluate ferroptosis in the presence of neurones, microglia / astrocytes & oligodendrocyte.
6.	Therapeutic Target	Most ferroptosis studies are cancer-related, limiting insights specific to ischemic stroke [152].	Examine methods for modifying ferroptosis to mitigate neuronal harm caused by ischemic stroke.

The above table no. 3 highlights challenges and future directions in ferroptosis research. It emphasizes the lack of unique markers distinguishing ferroptosis from other cell deaths and the need to identify specific markers. The unclear molecular mechanisms linking iron metabolism, lipid peroxidation, and ferroptosis warrant further exploration. The roles of iron-regulating proteins (e.g., TfR1, DMT1, ferroportin 1) in ferroptosis and other pathways remain uncertain, and the involvement of metals beyond iron is underexplored. Understanding ferroptosis' contribution to various brain cell functions, including neurons, microglia, astrocytes, and oligodendrocytes, is crucial. Lastly, most ferroptosis studies focus on cancer, limiting insights into its therapeutic potential for ischemic stroke, necessitating research on mitigating neuronal harm in such contexts.

CONCLUSION:

Ferroptosis may be involved in ischemia-induced inflammation, but the relationship is not defined and warrants more research. Generally, what is known about ferroptosis in ischemic stroke is heavily based on preclinical findings, stressing the urgent need for clinical research to test these findings. Targeting ferroptosis presents a promising avenue for neuroprotection; however, the roles of other programmed cell death (PCD) pathways, such as

apoptosis and autophagy, merit an evaluation in this context, with combination therapies to improve outcome. Optimizing treatment strategies, with the optimal timing of drug administration in the acute, subacute, and chronic phases of ischemic stroke, are also important. Hence, the basic and clinical research needs to be continued for the full unfolding of therapeutic potential of ferroptosis modulation in ischemic stroke.

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HOW TO CITE: Pavan Khodke, Pratiksha Khajone, Pankaj Fitwe, Atul Pawar, Milind Umekar, Rashmi Trivedi, Unlocking Potential: Ferroptosis Inhibitors As Promising Strategies for Ischemic Stroke Therapy, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, 2 (1), 400-424. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18206365>

